

ABSTRACT BOOK

Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon

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Acetic acid pretreatment effects on biogas production from sewage sludge

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Abstract: Recycling sewage sludge, is crucial for reaching carbon neutrality in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a cost-effective and easy process for reducing sludge pollution and converting organic fractions into value-added products. Sludge pretreatment prior to anaerobic fermentation is crucial for accelerating sludge hydrolysis and removing competing inhibitors. This study aimed to employ acetic acid as a non-aggressive acid, to directly treat sewage sludge in batch AD experiments. The objective was to evaluate the production of biogas from anaerobic digestion (AD) using raw sludge as substrate and supernatant after AD as inoculum, both taken from WWTP of nominal capacity of 150 000 equivalent per capita (EC). The total solids (TS) content of the raw sludge was 4.35%, and the volatile solids (VS) accounted for 74% (w/w) of TS. The evaluation of the methane production potential was performed in a bench-scale experiment using the biochemical methane potential (BMP) test in mesophilic conditions. The inoculum-to-substrate ratio used was 2:1. The dosages of acetic acid were in the range of 1 mM – 5 mM. The BMP tests lasted 10 days. Results showed that biogas production of AD batches with acetic acid pretreatment at 4 mM and 5 mM on AD were effectively enhanced, with the highest production being 2.7 and 3.6 times of that observed in control AD without acetic acid treatment. However, the AD batches with acetic acid treatment at low dosages of 1-3 mM had lower methane production (~1.5 times). The average VS removal effectiveness of 33% indicates a reduction of VS in the analyzed treatment. Total and soluble carbohydrates were consumed in AD process with an average percentage respectively of 74%-84%, while breakdown of total proteins concentration reach about of 40% at the highest dosage. Results show that acetic acid significantly promotes sludge disruption and increases dissolved material quantities and enhances the degradation and conversion of macromolecular organic matter (e.g., proteins and polysaccharides). Detailed mechanism will be elucidated in the future. The obtained results have to be considered as preliminary data to point out main characteristics and the anaerobic biodegradability of pre-treated sewage sludge.

Keywords: Anaerobic digestion, Sewage Sludge, Biogas, BMP tests

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